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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF BLOOD GLUCOSE IN DIABETIC PATIENTS
UNDERGOING DENTAL PROCEDURES**¹Rida Amjad, ²Muhammad Shoaib Amjad, ³Maryam Musaddiq¹Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore² Medical Officer at Tehrik e khidmat e insani general hospital jaranwala, Faisalabad³Jinnah Hospital Lahore**Article Received:** January 2019**Accepted:** February 2019**Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

Introduction: Diabetes mellitus, a world-wide increasing disease, is related to a heterogeneous group of metabolic disorders characterized by hyperglycemia resulting from either defects in secretion or insulin action or even both.

Aims and objectives: The basic aim of the study is to find the level of blood glucose in diabetic patients undergoing dental procedures. **Material and methods:** This study was conducted at Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore during 2018. The patients selected for this study were those who suffered from diabetes. The sample included only the patients who presented blood glucose levels and HbA1c demonstrating that diabetes was under control. They should also be under continuous oral hypoglycemic drugs treatment, medical supervision and no dose alterations. Blood pressure was measured using a digital sphygmomanometer and pulse oximetry and heart rate measured by pulse oximetry. **Results:** There is no statistically significant difference between the groups, regarding the evaluation period ($p > 0.05$). However, when comparing the periods statistically significant differences were observed ($p < 0.05$) for T2 and T3 values for group. For heart rate, there was no statistically significant difference between the groups regarding the evaluation period ($p > 0.05$). **Conclusion:** It is concluded that periodontal disease is the main oral clinical manifestation in diabetic patients. The anxiety level of patients neither varied significantly nor showed any correlation with the investigated hemodynamic parameters and glucose levels, regardless of whether local anesthetics were used.

Corresponding author:**Rida Amjad,**

Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus, a world-wide increasing disease, is related to a heterogeneous group of metabolic disorders characterized by hyperglycemia resulting from either defects in secretion or insulin action or even both. Many of the patients who seek dental care present systemic diseases, including diabetes, which are often unknown and not controlled [1]. For these risk patients, thorough anamneses are recommended in order to recognize their biological conditions and establish the clinical risks during the intervention. Moreover, the most critical the patient's systemic condition, the more important is the effective anxiety and pain control [2].

The successful use of local anesthesia is essential for good dental treatment as well as dentist and patient interaction in order to help anxious or dental phobic patients to achieve confidence. When pain is unexpectedly caused, there may be significant physiological changes during the dental procedures. With the evolution of local anesthetic solutions, their efficacy and clinical safety have been improved [3]. Nevertheless, there is still the possibility of systemic complications due to accidental intravascular injection, anesthetic inadequate choice, anesthetic overdose of salt or vasoconstrictor, unwanted drug interactions and more rarely, methemoglobinemia. Tooth extraction is one of the most common and frequent dental procedures, which is considered a stressful and painful intervention [4]. If patients' pain can be soothed, therapeutic procedures will be carried out in a more acceptable situation and patients' pain threshold will increase. Lidocaine is the most common local anesthetic material in dentistry [5]. Lidocaine was introduced by Nils Lofgren in 1943 and used for

the first time as a local anesthetic material in 1948. One of the most important concerns about local anesthetic injection is its systemic effects [6].

Aims and objectives

The basic aim of the study is to find the level of blood glucose in diabetic patients undergoing dental procedures.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study was conducted at Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore during 2018. The patients selected for this study were those who suffered from diabetes. The sample included only the patients who presented blood glucose levels and HbA1c demonstrating that diabetes was under control. They should also be under continuous oral hypoglycemic drugs treatment, medical supervision and no dose alterations. Blood pressure was measured using a digital sphygmomanometer and pulse oximetry and heart rate measured by pulse oximetry.

Statistical analysis

Student's t-test was performed to evaluate the differences in roughness between groups. Two-way ANOVA was performed to study the contributions. A chi-square test was used to examine the difference in the distribution of the fracture modes (SPSS 19.0 for Windows, SPSS Inc., USA).

RESULTS:

There is no statistically significant difference between the groups, regarding the evaluation period ($p > 0.05$). However, when comparing the periods statistically significant differences were observed ($p < 0.05$) for T2 and T3 values for group.

Table 01: Mean values and standard deviation of blood glucose (mg / dL) in the groups

Groups	T1	T2	T3	P values
G1	147.65 ± 40.18	149.9 ± 44.75	137.85 ± 35.86	*0.0425
G2	142.35 ± 34.83	144.1 ± 35.06	137.55 ± 38.66	0.0517
P values	0,3760	0,8813	0,9256	

For heart rate, there was no statistically significant difference between the groups regarding the evaluation period ($p > 0.05$). However, regarding the comparison between the periods statistically significant differences were observed ($p < 0.05$) for the T1 and T2 values for group.

Table 02: Mean values and standard deviation of heart rate (bpm)

Groups	T1	T2	T3	P values
G1	73.00 ± 12.47	77.90 ± 12.63	74.75 ± 13.03	*<0.05
G2	75.45 ± 12.49	77.35 ± 11.56	73.75 ± 11.86	0.5842
P values	0.4209	0.9108	0.3144	

DISCUSSION:

The purpose of this study was to determine if there was a significant correlation between anxiety levels, hemodynamics, and glucose parameters in patients undergoing dental treatment, regardless of whether or not they received a LAVA. No such relationship was found. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is one of the most frequent pathologies that dentists encounter. Its clinical importance springs from the possible occurrence of acute complications, whose severity could mean an immediate risk for the diabetic patient's life and require urgent diagnosis and treatment. DM includes a group of diseases characterized by impaired action or secretion of insulin, or both. There are four etiologic types of diabetes, although the most frequent are type 1 (90%) [8]. Prevalence of diabetes in adults worldwide was estimated to be 4% in 1995, and is predicted to rise to 5.4% by the year 2025. The countries with the largest number of people with diabetes are India, China and the U.S. In developing countries, the majority are in the age range of 45–64 years. In the developed countries, the majority of people with diabetes are aged 65 years. There are more women than men with diabetes. Besides that there was no statistically significant difference in blood glucose levels of patients undergoing both treatments suggesting the clinical feasibility of epinephrine or felypressin administration for patients with this profile [9]. The results of this study corroborate with Haji et al. and Khawaja et al. showing that the use of lidocaine associated to epinephrine does not present significant difference in the blood glucose alterations for compensated diabetic patients [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that periodontal disease is the main oral clinical manifestation in diabetic patients. The anxiety level of patients neither varied significantly nor showed any correlation with the investigated hemodynamic parameters and glucose levels, regardless of whether local anesthetics were used.

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